

Open Source Hardware Game - Manual

1. Overview

This is a cooperative board game designed for 3 to 6 players. The shared goal is to collaboratively improve and develop an Open Source Hardware (OSH) idea by guiding it through all stages of its lifecycle. Throughout the game, players encounter challenges, reflect critically, and identify value opportunities in their project. While working together, players can earn Coins by recognizing and articulating specific Value Dimensions. At the end of the game, the team evaluates both their collective progress and individual contributions.

2. Objective

Successfully guide a shared OSH project idea through all 6 lifecycle phases.

3. Duration

Estimated playing time: 45 to 90 minutes.

4. Number of Players

3–6 players.

5. Game Components

- 1 Game Board showing the 6 lifecycle phases: Development, Manufacturing, Distribution, Use, End of Life, and Basics.
- 6 Player Tokens.
- 1 Dice (D6).
- A deck of Question Cards.
- A set of Coins for tracking Value Dimension contributions.
- 6 notepads/Post-its for Lessons Learned after each phase.

6. Game Setup

- Choose a shared Open Source Hardware idea that all players will work on.
- Place all player tokens on the starting field of the first lifecycle phase: Development.
- Shuffle the Question Cards and place them face down.
- Place Coins next to the list of Value Dimensions.
- Assign someone to track Lessons Learned after each phase.

7. Game Structure & Phases

The OSH lifecycle is divided into 6 phases (Development, Manufacturing, Distribution, Use, End of Life, Basics), each with 8 fields. The 6 phases are based on the “Open Source Product Life Cycle” (Rabis, 2019), (Wille, 2017). Players roll the dice and move forward accordingly. If a rolled space is occupied, move to the next available space. To complete a phase, players must reach the final field; exact rolls are not required — if the roll exceeds, move directly to the last field. Multiple tokens may share the final field.

8. Field Types

Thinking Hats Fields

Reflect on the current lifecycle phase using one of Edward de Bono's Six Thinking Hats (de Bono, 1990):

- White (Facts): What do we know? What do we need to find out?
- Red (Feelings): What is your gut reaction? What emotions come up?
- Yellow (Benefits): What are the positives?
- Black (Cautions): What could go wrong?
- Green (Creativity): Think outside the box.
- Blue (Process): What is the process here?

Question Card Fields

Draw a Question Card and answer it when landing here. Each card includes a thought-provoking question and the perspective of a stakeholder (e.g., maker, supplier, competitor). The stakeholder role can relate to those identified during previous workshops.

9. Value Dimensions & Coins

There are 10 Value Dimensions (remodel.dk, 2018) that highlight how Open Source Hardware creates real-world value. If a player recognizes a Value Dimension during the game and explains its relevance to the current project, they earn 1 Coin.

The 10 Value Dimensions:

- Outsource your innovation: You no longer have to hire all the brilliant minds yourself — open source taps into global expertise.
- Customer goodwill: You level with your users and give them a sense of ownership and trust.
- Reduce development costs: Developers and engineers worldwide contribute, reducing R&D costs.
- Peer to peer support: Users support each other and deepen technical knowledge.
- Branding value: Building global communities of co-creators enhances your innovation image.

- Test ideas with the community: Users automatically test your features and provide feedback.
- Insight about customers & co-creation: Track firsthand what users want as they co-develop your product.
- Quality & validation: Thousands of eyes test your design early before release.
- Build on knowledge of global innovators: Enhance your product with open-source knowledge and designs.
- Make co-creation & participation easy: Clear tools and processes encourage broader participation.

10. Lessons Learned

To complete a phase:

- All players must reach the final field.
- Each player answers a final Question Card.
- As a group, reflect on the phase and document the Lessons Learned.

Focus points for Lessons Learned include:

- What key insights or decisions were made?
- Which features, structures, or principles were defined?
- Were any risks, challenges, or knowledge gaps identified?
- What questions remain open?

11. End of Game & Scoring

The game ends once all players have completed the Basics phase and documented final Lessons Learned.

There are two recognitions:

- Value Champion: The individual with the most Coins.
- Team Score: The total number of Coins earned by the entire team, representing collective impact.

12. Replay & Iteration

The game can be replayed iteratively, building on previously documented Lessons Learned. Alternatively, individual phases can be replayed to explore specific challenges or developments.

References

de Bono, E. (1990). *Six Thinking Hats*. London: Penguin Books.

Rabis, F. (2019). *Open Source Ökonomie - Konzept und Modellierung zur Effizienzmessung unserer Wirtschaft*. Diploma thesis.

remodel.dk. (2018). *Value Dimensions*. Retrieved from <https://remodel.dk/>

Wille, T. (2017). *Anforderungen an die Technischen Dokumentation bei Open Source Produktentwicklungsprozessen (OSPE)*. Master thesis.